

Metadata element	Content
Dataset title	AgriculturalParcel_CO2flux_France-Toulouse_0.30_15102018_15102019
Resource abstract	Set of agricultural parcels, with their geometry, crop type, value of CO ₂ flux (due to the crop vegetation cycle during an agricultural campaign year) and a few other attributes (intermediary results, quality information).
Responsible organisation	Agence de Paiement et de Services (ASP) – France
On-line resource	Zenodo
Topic Category	environment, farming
Keyword	CO2 flux, carbon, indicator, agricultural parcels, crop type
Geographic bounding box	min latitude 43,24 N min longitude 0,50 E max latitude 44,24 N max longitude 1,89 E
Spatial resolution	1: 5000
Spatial representation type	vector
Coordinate reference system	EPSG:32631 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 31N - Projected
Temporal coverage	start date: 15/10/2018 end date: 15/10/2019
Conditions for access and use	Licence CC0
Limitations on public access	None
Distribution format	shapefile files (compressed as ZIP)
Resource Language	eng
Lineage	Source IACS data: - RPG 2018 - https://geoservices.ign.fr/rpg#telechargementrpg2018 - Landscape features not extracted from the parcel geometry Temporal series of NDVI: - Sentinel 2 images used from 15/09/2018 to 15/10/2019 - Temporal NDVI series extracted from French national portal THEIA - MAJA mask used to detect cloudy areas Threshold - Default value (0.30) has been used